

IN-SITU DYNAMIC CHARACTERIZATION OF MARINE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Complete visco-elastic properties of composite materials are important for a number of design situations. The need ranges from baseline data requirements for damage detection to signature reduction. A number of well established techniques exist in a range of disciplines for these measurements. In this work, the dynamic response of thick E-glass vinylester samples is considered across a range of length scales and frequencies. Elastomeric matrix composites are also considered so that the assumption of time-temperature superposition is more strictly accurate. Particular emphasis is placed on the ability to diagnose matrix degradation in a marine environment. A new technique that combines information from dynamic mechanical analysis and ultrasonics is proposed. This technique will eliminate most of the existing boundary condition problems associated with dynamic mechanical analysis and allow matrix characterization to be performed in-situ for some types of applications. A basis for the measurements is presented that considers the non-destructive testing to be a part of a general polymer characterization toolbox, rather than a black-box. Implications of these measurements are considered for the particular mechanisms that are encountered in a marine environment. In particular the effect of damping measurement technique as an indicator of damage in composite materials is explored. Preliminary results for both field testing of sandwich composite boat hulls and laboratory controlled matrix curing will be shown.

The results show where this technique is applicable, the cases in which the technique is non-destructive and will compare the results to accepted characterization tools. Suggested mechanisms for degradation and process control in marine composites will also be considered.

BACKGROUND

Extensive effort has been directed toward the development of failure criteria and micro-mechanical evaluation of marine composites. Much of the focus and progress has been on tools to evaluate mechanisms of failure and load sharing from the micro-mechanics scale up to the continuum and structural length scales. These efforts have made it possible to intelligently design composite materials for particular applications, even when three-dimensional failure models are required. While work continues in a number of areas including sandwich panels and dynamic failure, this work has also begun to reach maturity in a number of areas. A need continues to exist for understanding how the mechanisms that are understood from a continuum scale relate to the mechanisms of cure and degradation mechanics of the molecular scale in both the polymeric matrix and the fibers. Extending this work has the potential to facilitate greater understanding of these mechanisms for application to quality control and in-service evaluation. Eventually, three aspects of the problem will need to be addressed: fiber failure and degradation, weak interphase and inadequate matrix properties. Matrix properties are perhaps the most important and also relates to a key aspect of quality control in composite parts.

More traditional non-destructive evaluation methods would require extension to be useful in this situation. In particular, it is important that the mechanisms of both the curing of the resin and degradation associated with the marine environment be considered. In particular, any claim to understand a relationship between strength and a measured quantity needs a firm foundation in the science of the material. Linear elastic deformation, or electromagnetic evaluation of the material as normally employed is not an appropriate tool for the prediction of strength of the composite. What is required is that a linkage be made between the characteristics of the matrix that provide reliability and high performance and measurements that can be made on the matrix. Ideally these measurements would be possible both in-situ and non-destructively. However, localized changes in specimens or the need to perform “biopsies” may be one alternative. Two common examples of quality control issues that should be addressed are: inadequate cross-linking of the vinyl ester due to insufficient catalyst or a need for a post-cure and inadequate cross-linking due to blockage caused by plasticization from excess catalyst. Additional degradation mechanisms for service may be also indicated by related techniques.

NEEDS STATEMENT FOR NEW TECHNIQUE

Development of a new technique for measuring matrix properties in vinyl ester resins used in marine composites is proposed. This technique will be applicable both to in-situ testing of the materials, as well as facilitating studies of degradation that may lead to premature failure of the material. Current polymer characterization techniques such as dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) or differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) are not well suited for use either in service or even in a production ship yard. In particular, specimen preparation is a problem for DMTA since the sample needs to be precisely shaped and flat in order to obtain repeatable results. It appears to be difficult to obtain quantifiable results from a specimen that is removed from a large component [1]. The repeatability results are consistent with previous research results for larger modal testing specimens where it was found that free boundary conditions needed to be used to perform quantitative damping measurements in composite materials [2, 3]. In contrast, while DSC can be performed under for partially reacted unreinforced resin, the characterization of the degree of cross-linking in a reinforced samples is difficult. This is particularly true for material that is approaching complete reaction when the number of unreacted sites is small, as is the case for most problems in composite manufacturing. In the case of partially reacted resin with reinforcement the expected error in the measurements that would result from preparation would be expected to be larger due to thermal effects on the specimen that result from preparation.

Thus linear elastic non-destructive and electromagnetic material testing methods are in general not well suited, for the evaluation of the vinyl ester matrices. At the same time some of the standard analytical tools such as DSC and DMTA cannot be applied to specimens that fully represent the conditions encountered in either manufacturing nor can they be applied to in-service inspection. The proposed techniques attempts to combine features of the analytical tools with existing field service techniques to provide in-situ analytical evaluation of the of matrices used in polymer matrix composites.

APPROACH

The Vinyl Ester Resin: The focus in the proposed work would be on reinforced and unreinforced vinyl ester resins. The vinyl ester resin consists of an epoxy backbone, for chemical resistance and high strength, combined with vinyl groups, for high reactivity, and styrene monomer, for low viscosity. A vinyl ester resin is made by reacting a di-epoxide with acrylic acid, or methacrylic acid (see figure 1). When you polymerize the vinyl groups, the unsaturated univalent radical $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-$, a crosslinked resin results. The vinyl groups (carbon to carbon double bonds) and ester linkages are only at the ends of the resin molecule. This controls the cross-linking density since the cross-linking can only occur at the end of the molecule, providing flexibility to the resin matrix. Also these groups at the end of the molecule are less likely to remain unreacted in the in the cured composite, providing fewer sites for chemical attack. The

ester linkages are adjacent to methyl groups, making them less susceptible to breakdown through hydrolysis. One problem with the vinyl ester resin is that the shelf life is limited. Free radicals are randomly created in the resin that then cure the resin. Inhibitors are therefore usually added to the vinyl esters to increase the shelf life. Thus as for most polymers, the objective of a test method would be to determine the degree of cross-linking in the polymer, to understand the number of unlinked sites that may be vulnerable to attack, and to evaluate crystallinity of the matrix. These aspects of the material would lead to either undesirable initial properties or degradation of the material with time. Quality control of marine composites requires that both the durability and initial quality of the composite be addressed.

Ultrasonic Measurements in polymers: To understand how polymers can be evaluated using ultrasonic methods, it is helpful to review the basic aspects of the problem. Previous work in this area has provided a number of specific examples but has not considered the application of the concepts to marine resins or composites in general [4]. Elastic properties determine the velocity of the ultrasonic wave through the solid. The degree of dispersion (which is the main physical measurement in acousto-ultrasonics) is determined by the damping of the material and the geometry of the specimen. In general then, most ultrasonic measurements are actually just a measure of the visco-elastic properties for a specimen of a particular geometry. This geometry must also be adjusted based on the wavelength in the solid to maintain a fixed ratio of the wavelength to the thickness. In general, this is not related to the strength of the solid, although modulus and damping are commonly used in as a part of the process used to interpret the bonding characteristics of a material. Perturbation of the visco-elastic characteristics is the basis for techniques that are used to characterize the interatomic potentials of many materials.

Figure 1: Vinyl ester resin formed by reacting a di-epoxide with acrylic acid. When the vinyl groups polymerize (CH₂=CH—) a crosslinked resin results.

These same techniques can also be used to evaluate the degree of cross-linking between the molecules in polymeric and elastomeric materials. While limited work has considered the effect of this idea on ultrasonic testing, the same conceptual framework that underlies other analytical method such as DMTA. A brief review of the conceptual framework follows with an application of the idea. The following discussion describes how this is applicable to the evaluation of elastomeric materials such as those used as matrix materials in marine composites.

As the initial basis for the discussion, the bulk modulus is defined as:

$$K_T = -V \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial V} \right)_T \quad \text{Eqn. 1.}$$

For an ultrasonics, the measurements are adiabatic which makes them differ somewhat from a static measurement that is isothermal. Combining this definition with the second law of thermodynamics, we obtain:

$$K_T = V \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial V^2} \right)_T - TV \left(\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial V^2} \right)_T \quad \text{Eqn. 2.}$$

for polymers, the second term is negligible, so that

$$K_T \approx V \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial V^2} \right)_T \quad \text{Eqn. 3.}$$

the energy term dominates and the entropy term can be neglected. Thus the bulk modulus depends on the volume dependence of the intermolecular energy. If reasonable assumptions about the form of the intermolecular potential are made, the bulk modulus can be calculated as a function of the volume [5]. Obviously because of the much higher modulus along the polymer chains, the primary factor in the modulus of the polymer is modulus between the chains. As the degree of crystallinity of a given polymer increases, its specific volume nearly always decreases which causes an increase in the acoustic velocity.

Figure 2: Schematic of the change in peak of wave speed with degree of cross-linking.

Similarly, cross-linking decreases the specific volume of a polymer. Plasticization increases specific volume and thus decreases the ultrasonic velocity. However, this discussion is incomplete. Low temperature and high temperature behavior of polymers are quite different. In addition to molecular separation, the sound speed is influenced by structural rearrangement. Structural rearrangements take a finite time referred to as a relaxation time, τ . Thus the time constant introduces a frequency dependence for the structural rearrangement measurements. Thus, at the glass transition, the sound speed rapidly decreases. Similarly, the peak in the absorption of the ultrasonic wave occurs at:

$$\omega \tau = 1 \quad \text{Eqn. 4.}$$

The Arrhenius relation then gives the relation between the temperature and the relaxation time as:

$$\tau = \tau_0 e^{\Delta H/RT} \quad \text{Eqn. 5.}$$

where ΔH is the activation energy for the structural rearrangement and τ_0 is constant. From equation 5 and data on the combined change in temperature and time, the effects of the temperature on activation energy can be determined.

Experimental Verification: The previous discussion of mechanisms in thermal analysis and ultrasonics is quite similar to that used for a DMTA. A key element of the work will be to fill in the existing understanding of thermal mechanical analysis in a manner that creates the foundation for the proposed thermo-acoustic testing. Unlike the DMTA, however, an ultrasonic measurement though a layer has defined boundary condition that can be controlled to eliminate the impact on the measurement. The edge of the sample must be at a sufficient number of wavelengths from the transducer to be modeled as an unbounded layer. Further, the use of time reversal excitation and even phased arrays can make it possible to select the particular layer that is interrogated with the technique. This has great potential for future development of the technique for in-service inspection where a particular layer may be of concern due to chemical contamination, fire or water incursion. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the data that would be produced from such a system. In particular, the shift in the peak of the curve based on the change in temperature will result in value that can be assembled to obtain the activation energy.

To determine if the technique is applicable to material systems of interest to in marine applications, both reinforced and unreinforced vinylester resins have been considered as well as the filled material that is used to bond the core to the face sheet material. A key element in the quality of matrix is the availability of catalyst for the required cross-linking to occur. In contrast, excess catalyst will block the cross-linking and serve as a plasticizer. Thus the amount of catalyst is expected to have an optimal value that is associated with the required material properties. This is a complex problem because of the interplay between the resin chemistry and the environment. However, for a particular batch of resin under controlled conditions, the amount of catalyst should be controllable in the same way a gel test is performed to evaluate the rate.

APPLICATION TO FACE SHEET BONDING

One example of the marine composites quality will be used to demonstrate the potential for applications of thermal acoustic analysis. In this case a question arose with a new boat with possible quality control problems related to the core to face sheet binding. The particular boat was similar to a traditional design for a lobster boat, but with yacht trim and finished as a pleasure boat. This is the type of boat that would be referred to as a “lobster yacht” in some regions, but was changed somewhat in form for use as a pleasure cruiser. The boat, like most of its type, was constructed of a cored composite hull. In this case

the hull was hand laid up in separate layers with an end grain balsa core material, and vinylester outer face sheet and polyester resin inner face sheet. The problems identified in the face sheet bonding to the core were based on a marine survey. Problems were found with the hull after the boat was fitted out when the marine surveyor performed a tap test. Some further evidence of a possible problem with the core bonding material resulted from the failure of the bond between the outer face sheet and the core when the engine vents were cut and when holes were drilled for the through hull fittings. One of the cut sections was sent to the core bond vendor for laboratory evaluation. The core bonding putty vendor found in an ASTM D-1062 test that the bond between the outer face sheet and the core was approximately 87% of the laboratory values. This is a reasonable value for a boatyard built production panel. However more suggestive of a problem was the lack of a complete cure in the bond. Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) tests indicated that the putty was not fully cured. The large peak in the thermal analysis curves suggests that post-curing of the putty was occurring in the DSC. This suggests that while the measured strength was quite reasonable, at least a portion of the putty may have been insufficiently cured.

A plan of attack was developed for evaluating the problem. In this case a needs exits for a field-testing approximation to ASTM D-1062. The test would be used to evaluate the strength of the bond putty that was used to adhere the core to the outer face sheet. A fixture was developed and a test panel was built. The methods and materials of the test panel were the same as those used when the hull in question was built. All testing was then performed either in the boat yard on the hull or the panel testing and procedure development was done at the University of Maine Crosby laboratory. Field tests on the hull are based on the use of this test fixture and qualitative pry tests of the laminate on the hull.

Another panel was also tested which used a similar configuration of materials, end grain balsa, core-bonding material was also obtained from a different boat yard. Comparison data then is shown which includes the test panel, a small panel from a second boat yard, as well and another panel from the deck of the same boat that was built with a different crew. In the boat as well as the test panel the lay-up is gelcoat, 2 layers of 1 ½ oz matte and a layer of 1708 and 1808 all in a vinylester resin matrix. The core is ¾” end grain balsa with an interior facesheet of 2 layers of 1808 in a polyester resin matrix.

Figure 3: Port side of boat showing some of the locations of points at which samples were removed.

FIELD TEST FIXTURE

The field tests fixture used was based on the concept of pulling on the edge of the top laminate and determining the adhesion of the facesheet to the core. The design would have ideally included a method to eliminate the need to undercut the top facesheet. The undercut was required to mechanically grab the facesheet for pulling. The ASTM D-1062 test uses an adhesive bonded fixture, however the time required for curing of the adhesive made that approach less than ideal as well. It was determined that the edge notching would be accepted as the cost of having a simple field-test method. The problems with the method were overcome at least in part by making both reference laminated panels from the original boat builder and from several other boat yards. Those panels could then be compared to the results for the boat with a sufficient number of tests done in all cases to allow the variability of the results to be understood as well as improving the technique required on the practice panel. The test fixture is shown in Figure 3.

Results from the test panels are shown below with comments on the failure mode. In general the likelihood of failure at the facesheet bond is enhanced with the test technique used, but the numbers do give some indication of the general quality of the bond. Because of the notching at the adhesive bond, brittle adhesives with higher notch sensitivity will produce lower results than would be expected in service. The numbers obtained for the core bond would thus be lower than what would be expected for the fully bonded panels, but would approximate the design strength of the bond that would surround a small delamination of the face sheet. A delamination that occurs in manufacturing is a similar notch and the performance of the core bond in this case would be well represented by this test. Data from test panels show reasonable consistency and give an idea of the expected load.

Figure 4: Test fixture used to measure adhesion between the facesheet and the core on the boat and on test panels.

Manufacturer	Test	Load (lbs.)	Failure
Boat Yard 1	1		
	2		
	3	305	At back of core on rear face sheet
	4	386	At back of core on rear face sheet
	5	417	At core to face sheet bond
Boat Yard 1 with post-cure	1	159	At core to face sheet bond
	2	434	At core to face sheet bond
	3	328	At core to face sheet bond
	4	438	At core to face sheet bond
Boat Yard 2	1	307	At bond to backing sheet
	2	385	Core bond to face sheet

Table 1: basic tests on panel with and without post cure and for the reference panel used for evaluation of the fixture.

A total of 19 locations were tested on the hull. Semi-quantitative results were obtained from the first 10 test locations (shown in table 2), and qualitative tests were performed in 9 additional locations. The vast majority of those failures occurred in the region of the putty bond between the face sheet and the core material. Pry tests were performed on an additional eight locations to determine the extent of the brittle putty. Results are qualitative for the later locations, but are meant to be a supplement to the more quantitative results.

Sample	Load (lbs.)	Failure Mechanisms/Observations
1	555	Failure at inner face sheet – Stbd forward of engine vent on shear
2	395	Putty bond, portion of core followed with outer face sheet -- Stbd aft of engine vent
3	315	Putty bond, small portion of core followed with outer face sheet -- Stbd on bottom ~ middle
4	358	Putty bond, small portion of core followed with outer face sheet -- Stbd on bottom ~ aft of #3
5	<30	Failed at bond to face sheet, no putty on ½ of area. Core seam was dry with gap – Port on bottom ~ 9 ft. from bow
6	82	Failed at bond to face sheet, no putty on ½ of area. Core seam was dry– Port on bottom ~ aft of midline
7	738	Failed at bond to face sheet, no putty, bond was resin to core, no core followed with outer face sheet – Port on bottom ~ aft of midline
8	97	Putty bond, no core followed with outer face sheet – port on shear ~ 4 ft. aft of engine vent
9	<30	Putty bond, no core followed with outer face sheet – Port on shear ~ 3 ft. forward of engine vent
10	191	Putty bond, no core followed with outer face sheet – port on bottom ~ forward about 6 inches below boot top

Table 2: Hull tests taken across a broad range of areas of the finished boat.

THERMO-ACOUSTIC TESTING

Based on the results of the mechanical test, the thermo-acoustic technique was used to evaluate the response of the putty used in the bonding of the outer face sheet to the core. In this case, the heating of the sample was performed at fixed temperature of 120°C, with the times chosen to maintain the heat transfer into the sample, and to move from curing temperatures into the temperature range at which degradation occurs in the putty. This degradation temperature range was based on previous mechanical testing of the sample. All testing was performed in air. While this test was performed on the test panels because of problems that were encountered with heating of the hull, even in the areas of through hull fitting, the technique is applicable to testing of the finished hull.

Most notable in the response of the putty is the change in the acoustic impedance (the product of the ultrasonic wave speed and the density) with the length of time at temperature. The middle line in figure 5 is the initial cure of the core bonding putty as tested from the panel. The upper signal, showing an increase in the reflected energy (higher acoustic impedance) is after curing for 10 minutes at temperature. After 20 minutes the signal is lower than the initial signal indicating that the breakdown had begun to occur in the samples. Error for each test was not considered at this point in the program and may be a factor depending on the amount of core bond used and the initial degree of cross linking. The sequence of curves in this case suggests that insufficient catalyst was used in the putty for the conditions.

Figure 5: Figure showing the effect of the time at fixed temperature on the core bond from panel 1.

CONCLUSIONS FROM APPLICATION

Given the variability of the mechanical testing method and the surface preparation, the tests on the panels and the boat hull appear to show reasonable bonding between the face sheet and the core on the starboard side. The variation observed is at a level to be expected in normal boat building or any composite construction practice. Care should be exercised to note any area that would form an initiation site for core disbond however since the core bonding material is quite brittle. The port side of the boat shows signs of outer skin bonding that is below what would be expected from normal variation of the hull. The core is imperfectly bonded to the face sheet in this region either due to incomplete cure or the existence of some contaminant, or excess catalyst, in the putty that is functioning as a plasticizer.

This is conceptually consistent with the DSC tests that showed that the cure could be obtained during testing and is also consistent with the new technique that was presented. The new technique has the potential to be applied in-situ with a simple ultrasonic system and a heat source. This is a quality test that is suitable for a boat yard and can be done with simple low cost equipment. More rigorous investigation of this idea must be done in order to develop a good technique that could be used for quality control in production boatyard environment.

FUTURE WORK

Extension of this work beyond the initial application would be expected to be done in collaboration with a polymer chemist and researchers familiar with failure mechanisms in marine composite materials. The technique will provide a method for the evaluation of mechanisms in these materials and may provide insight into proper quality control techniques for use in manufacturing. Thus leveraging activities both in the more applied structural areas as well as looking at the basic science of matrix degradation and failure will be facilitated by the successful completion of the proposed research program.

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